

Social Environment Support Towards Leisure Time Activities Of Youth In Malaysia

Nurul Hidayati Hamid, Mohd Mahzan Awang, Abdul Razaq Ahmad, Jamsari Alias

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 07 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Social Environment Support, Leisure Time Activities, Family Support, Peer Support, Community Support</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5555378</p>	<p><i>This research was conducted to identify the state of social support towards the leisure time activities of different ethnic youths in Malaysia. Social environment support refers to family support, peer support and community support. Leisure time activities apply to education, sports, religious, family, community and economy. This study was attended using survey questionnaires that were distributed to 1184 youths of different ethnics in the north, east, south and west. Data gathered was analysed employing the descriptive test. The result revealed that family support had the highest mean, 4.01, while peer support and community support was at the average mean of 3.91 and 3.83, respectively. This study's significance confirmed that family influenced the use of leisure time activities among youths. The youths that received high surrounding support would actively join activities in their leisure time. Therefore, effort must be made to bring awareness for peers and the community to become the principal supporting factor.</i></p>

Introduction

Youths that engage in leisure time activities hold a positive impression on their well-being. The use of leisure time activities is linked as the best medium for youths' development in which it provides space and opportunity for them to advance their potential through activities contained in it (Jalloh 2013). This opportunity is vital for the youths to grow in these aspects; intellectual, psychological, social, moral and ethics. There are various activities youths can engage in, according to their interest and needs. The empirical proof attested that structured activities are linked to well-being, particularly in physical and mental viewpoints (Badura et al.2015; Kim 2015). Many local and international research pieces defined leisure time as activities that can be done independently and related to positive experience (Newman, Tay &Diener 2013; Chen, Li &Chen 2013). Nevertheless, this research viewed how youths' leisure time activities were influenced by the social institution that provides the right opportunity for them to be executed as raised by Camara, Bacigalupe& Padilla (2017). Social environment plays a pivotal position in youth development and advancement. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the factors that influence the youths' leisure time activities to encourage continuous participation and contribute to their well-being.

Participation of youths in leisure time activities is believed to enhance the learning process and forming their personalities (Syed Lamsah, Mohd Imran &SareenaHanim 2018). Youth is a phase in which a person is undergoing novelties in physical, social and cognitive realms. During this period, youths require support from social institutions such as family, friends and the surrounding community to meet their needs, particularly in filling their leisure time. It is imminent to help the youth from getting involved in any social misconduct. Through participation in leisure time activities, the youths can socialise and communicate with the community. Besides, it is believed that social support can assist growing youths' minds (Azyyati, Fariza&SalasiaHanim 2013).

Youth is a period when a person seeks freedom, challenges and desires. The youth often make their decision and become independent of their family. A grown mind prompts shifts in attitude to determine their lifestyle. During this phase, the youth try to discover their identities and seek freedom from their parents. They tend to spend more time with their peers and form their cliques, transforming the synergy between parents and their children. According to Vokacova et al. (2016), peer pressure frequently happened during leisure time as much free time is spent with the peers instead of the parents. When the children grow up, the time allocated on family activities decreases, modifying the control, and the information parents hold of their children's activities (Keijsers&Poulin, 2013). Nevertheless, parents' presence is still quintessential in this phase to secure fitting development for the youth even though they tend to be isolated from their parents (Viner et al. 2012). Parents play an inherent role in most aspects of the youth's life, including leisure time. The parents must address the

proper education for the youth to promote a good personality and attitude. Therefore, the support from parents, peers and the community will help achieve remarkable development during the transition process to adulthood.

The correct social setting will benefit in moulding a positive youth (Taylor et al. 2017). According to Gal (2017), to comprehend a person, someone needs to discern the characteristics that affect one's action and the influence of the socio-cultural environment towards one's growth. Social environment factor has to be taken into account to encourage the youth to join leisure time activities. An appropriate environment is required to inspire an excellent behavioural development of the youth. Support from the parents is essential as children are under the supervision and control of their parents before they shift into youth. Parents are the closest socialisation agent for the children. Consequently, parents play a crucial purpose in raising children (SitiNurshahizan, 2014).

Youth that leads a sedentary lifestyle will have deteriorating physical agility and is connected to social predicaments such as feeling left out and dependent. Social isolation is ironically one of the most severe quandaries in this epoch in which connection is easily accomplished (Glover, 2017). This situation will jeopardise the health, well-being and quality of lives for many adults and older people in the future (Nicholson, 2012). Social isolation is relevant to depression and congestive heart disease. Preventing and reducing social isolation and loneliness in adults is one of the requisite researches in leisure study. Nonetheless, there is still a lack of report on victorious intervention to reduce social isolation (Cattan et al., 2005).

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Social support is the presence of a person that can assist, care, cherish and love another. The support that is given is expected to cultivate the spirit and motivate the person to do something in his capacity. The support given empowers the youth to expand a skill and decide (Caldwell & Witt 2011). For example, parents who recognise their children's potential will motivate them to learn a skill, helping them advance. Support from parents also allows youth in voicing out one's view and making a decision. Social support also aids an individual solving a behavioural issue and give one the energy to handle any arising obstacle. Support can be given through advice, positive feedbacks, empathy and expression (Chapman et al. 2017).

Family is the most critical socialisation agent because children spend a considerable amount of time in the family setting (Đurišić&Bunijeva 2017). Family teaches skills and establishes trust that can help strengthen a character related to physical activities. Support from the family encompasses many forms; (i) trust and attitude towards leisure time activities (ii) role model, (iii) involvement and (iv) providing facilities such as payment of fees. Youths are more comfortable asking for help if the source of support comes from an individual that can be trusted, close and has a healthy relationship with them. Apart from that, peers also play an absolute position in influencing youth's attitude towards leisure time activities (Chandrasekaran et al. 2018). During the transition period from a child to youth, children apportion more time with their peers. According to Santos, Kornienko& Rivas-Drake (2017), peers are considered one of the most critical social components during childhood and youth. Peers are a vital connection for a developing youth to learn the skills necessitated in life. In this context, the relationship with peers is indispensable in realising socio-emotional and identity.

Next, the surrounding community also plays a primary position in youth development because the surrounding community is an institution for the youth and children as they provide opportunities to interact with society (Sichlinga&Plöger 2018). According to Sichlinga&Plöger, youth allot more time outside of the family context and expand their social connection and circles. The relationship built is deemed imminent because the community can provide resources that are not available in the family. Thus, the surrounding community is imperative in developing youth. Thus, family, peers and community possess potent influences for the youth to be involved in leisure time activities. A suitable environment will help the youth in growing self-potential in a broader societal role. Hence, research needs to look into the catalyst that causes youth to get involved in leisure time activities. Thus, the support and motivation are quintessential to help developing youth, impacting themselves, family and the community.

Bronfenbrenner Ecology Theory

This research was conducted according to Ecology System Theory that was brought up by Bronfenbrenner (1979). This theory is the most suitable theory to evaluate how the support of the surrounding environment influences leisure time activities and life well-being through layers of the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. It explains how the surrounding influences an individual in joining leisure time activities and how it contributes to life well-being, as mentioned in the research question. Bronfenbrenner ecology theory highlighted the individual who went through the growth and development process encompassed in a system that emphasises interaction with one another. Nevertheless, this particular study looked at three different supports from Bronfenbrenner (1979) that were, parents, peers and the

surrounding community. This research was based on the assumption that parents, peers, and surroundings represent social environment support. This study intended to identify social environment support, the use of leisure time activities, and youths' life well-being from different ethnics in Malaysia according to gender, ethnics, and socio-economy status. This research was attended to survey the relationship and influence of parents, peers, and the surrounding community using leisure time and the contribution of leisure time with youth's life well-being.

Research Methodology

Respondents were made up of 1184 Malaysian youths, aged between 19 to 24 years, ranging from Malay, Chinese and Indian. The selection of states was made by random sampling representing four zones. These zones were north, south, middle and east, from multiple ethnics. Descriptive statistics were employed to view and describe thoroughly on the level of surrounding support. Descriptive analysis was also adopted to describe the profile of respondents thoroughly and to answer the research questions.

Instrument Development

Researchers developed items based on previous research while using Exploratory Factor Analysis to confirm the number of constructs to measure the aspect of surrounding social support. This section is composed of 18 built items to evaluate the level of surrounding social support on youth involvement, and it is made up of three constructs. These constructs were the support of parents, peers, and the surrounding community built according to previous research. The instrument for surrounding social support consisted of 18 items. After the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted, two items were omitted, and 16 items were left in the instrument. These 16 items were five items for family support, five items for peer support and six items for surrounding community support and the instrument was chosen using five Likert scale options; 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (moderately agree), 4 (agree), 5 (strongly agree). EFA test that was conducted confirmed that there were three constructs for surrounding social support.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Research Demography

One thousand one hundred eighty-four respondents who were youths of different ethnics from four zones were the northern zone represented by Pulau Pinang, middle zone represented by Selangor, Eastern Zone represented by Pahang, and the Southern zone represented by Johor were involved in this study. The age of the respondents was between 19 to 24 years old. The detail of the demographic profile of the research is as below.

Table 4.1 Frequency and Percentage of Demography of Respondents

Profile	Demography	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	495	41.8%
	Female	689	58.2%
Ethnic	Malay	602	50.8%
	Chinese	340	28.7%
	Indian	242	20.4%
Income	No income	683	57.7%
	<RM1,000	111	9.4%
	RM1,001-RM2,000	149	12.6%
	RM2,001-RM3,000	117	9.9%
	>RM3,001	124	10.5%
Level of Education	SPM	346	29.2%
	STPM/Matriculation/	109	9.2%
	Diploma	454	38.3%
	Degree	220	18.6%
	Master	41	3.5%
	PhD	14	1.2%

As seen in Table 4.1 above, the demography of the respondents included 495 males and 689 females. As for ethnics, 602 respondents were Malay (50.8%), 340 Chinese respondents (27.8%) and 242 Indian respondents (20.4%). These respondents were sufficient to represent the youth population-based on ethnics in Malaysia. 111

respondents involved in this research had an income of below RM1000, 149 respondents had an income between RM1001 – RM2000, 117 respondents had an income of RM2001 – RM3000, and 124 respondents had more than RM3001 for their income. As for education level, 346 respondents were at SPM level, 109 of the respondents had STPM/Matriculation/Diploma, 454 respondents have a Diploma, 220 respondents had a degree followed 41 respondents with a Master Degree, and lastly, only 14 respondents had a PhD.

Next, a descriptive analysis that included mean and the standard deviation was conducted to determine the level of surrounding social support of different ethnics in Malaysia. The result of the descriptive analysis conducted is in the table below.

Table 1.2 Total Level of Surrounding Social Support

Item	Min	S.D	Interpretation
Family Support	4.01	0.68	High
Peer Support	3.91	0.69	Moderately High
Surrounding Community Support	3.83	0.75	Moderately High
Total Mean	3.92	0.62	Moderately High

Generally, surrounding social support of different ethnics measured according to three constructs: family support, peer support, and surrounding community support were at a moderately high level. In details, family support had a high mean. It attested that most families do not object to the youth being involved in leisure time activities. However, these findings contradicted the conclusions of (OpićadanĐuranovića (2014) that family support decreases as youth spend a lot more time with their peers as they grow old. Nonetheless, support from peer and surrounding community does not play a notable role in motivating the youth to utilise their leisure time. These findings were following Goswami (2012) research that stated that peer and community give less support in the youth involvement in leisure activities.

Table 4.3 Level of Social Surrounding Support for Family Aspect

Statement	Min	S.D	Interpretation
Involve in various educational activities	4.15	0.92	High
Join sports and recreational activities	4.07	0.86	High
Join religious activities	4.19	0.86	High
Involve in activities organised by the surrounding community	3.87	0.90	Moderately High
Join economic activities	3.79	0.98	Moderately High
Total Mean	4.01	0.68	High

In parts, surrounding social support in family aspects towards increasing youths' involvement and interest in different ethnics in leisure time activities was high. Most families in Malaysia do not object to their children in joining leisure time activities, including knowledge, sports and recreation, religious and other activities. These findings were identical to Bronfenbrenner and Morris' (2005) research that declared that parents are an essential ingredient to fashion and develop children's attitude and health because parents act as the guard for children in joining leisure time activities. These conclusions were also supported by the study of ZarinahArshatdanRozanaJapara (2018) that proved that family influences youth's attitude in enhancing life quality and well-being. The family also affords opportunities for the individual to share activities and expand one's emotion. Supervising leisure time could prevent the youth from getting involved in illicit activities.

The research findings also reported that the family plays a role in youths' involvement in religious activities. Formal or non-formal religious activities is a process of forming the character of an individual. Religious activities can prevent youth from performing social dilemmas and preventing issues that are opposed to their religious beliefs. These verdicts were approved by (Irma, NorlizahdanFathiyah, 2017), which maintained that connecting to spiritual activities could resolve spiritual problems rising in children these days. Parents who

went to religious activities such as religious talks will teach their children to respect the elders, compromise, and help one another.

Another activity that is supported by parents is from the educational aspect. Findings showed that support of family for educational activities was satisfactory. This manifested that parents were concerned about their children's education to increase their social status. The literature also showed that parents of different ethnics support their children to succeed by providing their needs and guidance, whether at home or in school. Parents that spend their time reading with their children will foster a passion for studying in their children, thus expanding their learning. Parents that are involved in their children's study will be able to find out their needs. IrwanFariza, Abdul RazaqdanMohdMahzan (2018) confirmed that academic success is achievable if the parents are included in the children's education.

However, family support in community activities was still under satisfactory. It symbolised the lack of participation of families in community activities. It happened due to the individualistic attitude of the people in a community. According to Hazlina, Fatimah and MarlyanaAzziyati (2014) hectic working life is one factor that causes the community's lack of interaction. It is because every family member is occupied with their commitment. Family, especially parents, need to interact and know the neighbours. Families should instil collectivism value among family members. Families that raise children in a collectivist community will inspire children to build comprehensive connection, teamwork and not beselfish. The best connection among families and communities can create a safe and harmonious surrounding. This outcome was supported by KhairudinCheTak (2017), who asserted that a community's happiness is influenced by a good relationship between other individuals and family members.

Meanwhile, for family's support towards economy activities aspect, it was at a moderately high level. It indicated that parents were less encouraging of their children to be involved in economic activities. It was because parents were not exposed to such activities. This conclusion further strengthened the research by Aristizábal et al. (2018) where parents' non-involvement in economic activities are causing them not to explain the advantages of economic activities to the youths. Parents should expose children to relevant economic knowledge from an early age to prepare children in the future. Studies discovered that youths tend to be involved in economic activities in entrepreneurship activities when their parents are involved in the activity. Economic knowledge is requisite to help youths face the challenge of globalisation nowadays.

Table 1.2 Level of Social Surrounding Support for Peer Aspect

Statement	Mean	S.D	Interpretation
Join the Educational Program	3.94	0.93	Moderately High
Involve in various religious Programs	3.9	0.89	Moderately High
Join family activities	4.07	0.83	High
Join community activities	3.88	0.87	Moderately High
Involve in economic development activities	3.67	1.01	Moderately High
Total Mean	3.91	0.69	Moderately High

Next, the findings for surrounding support for peer aspects in increasing participation and interest of the youth of multiple ethnics towards leisure time were moderately high. Majority of the youths in Malaysia experience lack of engagement in leisure time activities. These activities come in the forms of education, religion, community and economy development programs. It happened because youths tend to choose fun activities with their peers. Nevertheless, the results determined that peer support in participation in family activities was high. Public interaction between family members in social media allowed peers to join in the discussion. By sharing photos, activities and messages, social media created a platform in which family members and peers interact. These findings were similar to SitiEzaleila Mustafa (2016), which affirmed that social media aims to bring family members and peers closer. The progression of the current technology causes the communication media to advance, especially on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. The society chooses

these platforms to build and strengthen the relationship with peers and family members. Connectivity through social media holds exciting characteristics that can be used to uphold unity in society.

The findings also revealed that peer support for community and economic activities was at a low level. It is because rendezvous with peers was deemed a time to do something fun and share happiness. It contradicts with participation in community activities that are considered restricted activities. Peer is the main factor for participation in community activities. Research by Yusri Ibrahim (2017) noted that peer that is continuously involved in community activities such as social community, societal activities, community sports program and others would directly encourage the youth to participate in this activity. It noted that the factor that encourages the participation of youth in leisure time activities is peer pressure.

Table 1.3 Level of Social Surrounding Support for Surrounding Community Aspect

Statement	Mean	S.D	Interpretation
Organising education-related activities	3.83	0.98	Moderately High
Organising activities related to sports and recreation	3.89	0.92	Moderately High
Providing facilities to ease religious programs	3.96	0.92	Moderately High
Organising activities that involve family members	3.94	0.91	Moderately High
Organising programs that involve all the members of the community	3.78	0.96	Moderately High
The program that was organised encouraged economy based activities	3.61	1.03	Moderately High
Total Mean	3.83	0.75	Moderately High

The outcome determined that surrounding social support for the local community in increased leisure time for the youth of different ethnics was at a moderately high level. These findings revealed that the local community did not encourage participation for activities in the community. These findings were reciprocal to (SitiHajar, Noralina&Zaiton 2017) that highlighted that people in Sarawak's activities outskirts are passive because of the failure of the community in organising programs to encourage the participation of the youth. The community on every level need to draft formal or informal programs to encourage the participation of youth. The harmony of a community is determined by the interaction and the social relationship among the community. A united community can be developed through community members' participation in organised programs to create a share of values. The association of community can shape teamwork and respect among each other, which becomes the foundation for developing a peaceful community. Lavdmaa, Bolorchimeg& Mamoru (2018) highlighted that activities managed in a living area could increase individual awareness and responsibility as a community member responsible and conscientious on their surroundings.

These results confirmed that the involvement in sport and recreation was at moderate to a high level. It recorded that the community was less supportive of youths' involvement in sports activities in the community. The community's organisation of sport and recreation programs such as sports carnival, annual sports program, and monthly sports competition needs to be increased to encourage youths' more involvement. A variety of sports organisations and the local community's frequency manifest unity among youths and increase body fitness and prevent dangerous diseases. The local community also plays a role in organising community activities, which are the activities that involve all community members, such as societal and cultural activities. These cultural activities are Eid al-Fitr, Chinese New Year, Deepavali and many more. The organisation of activities that include community members irrespective of the religion and race enables youth and community to create understanding and respect among society in Malaysia. It coincided with MohdRusYunus and ZulfagarMamat (2007) statement, in which they stated that the celebration of festivities could increase tolerance among multiple nations and races society in this country. Besides, societal activities such as collaborative work which involve all community members could develop positive values among youths and community. It coincides with NorazrineTahar's research, Abdul Razaq Ahmad and MohdMahzanAwang (2017), which discovered that the association of younger generation in societal activities could improve volunteer spirit, racial unity and helping practice which will develop good identity.

The organisation of activities which stresses religious elements can also develop spiritual values which need to be inculcated in younger generations so that the development of human capital keeps flourishing in a more challenging life. The involvement of the community could help to intensify tolerance among multiple ethnic youths in Malaysia. According to research done by SitiHajar and Haris (2005), this statement pronounced that all facets of living in a community own a critical impact on community members' behaviour, especially the younger ones. In the organisation of economy-based activities, the community is seen as lacking in support to youths in preparing various economy based programs. Youths should be exposed to economy-related knowledge, especially information to manage finance. This discovery was per Xiao and Oneil (2016) research, in which finance education increases the knowledge and builds confidence in their financial management. The lack of knowledge related to financial management is often linked to the mental problem among youths. Additionally, the community needs to coordinate entrepreneurship-related plans and invite a thriving youth icon. A right role model could intensify the youth's spirit by sharing their experiences in the entrepreneurship domain. The organisation of entrepreneurship based programs would allow youths to practice their skills, giving them the space to fill their leisure time with activities that could lift the economy. The genuine opportunity gained could provide youths with fair knowledge and skills to face current circumstances.

Conclusion

Ergo, it can be concluded that family, peers, and surrounding community support is all-important to encourage youths' continuous involvement during leisure time. It proves that the effort to develop youth's potential needs to be implemented holistically by all the relevant authorities. All of these support factors contribute a meaningful influence on the youth's use of leisure time activities. Multiple authorities need to play their part in constructing appropriate activities to encourage youth participation to the optimum level to ensure that youths are actively committed in leisure time and recreational activities. Government and NGO bodies must design and arrange programs in cultivating positive attitudes among youths. Sound control of leisure time can prevent youths from being involved in social misconduct.

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Author Information

Nurul Hidayati Hamid

Faculty of Education, The National University of Malaysia

Mohd Mahzan Awang

Faculty of Education, The National University of Malaysia

Abdul Razaq Ahmad

Faculty of Education, The National University of Malaysia

Jamsari Alias

University Citra Center, The National University of Malaysia
